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В данной статье рассматриваются механизмы и методы корпусной лингвистики, опыт изучения, анализа, систематизации лингвистической работы посредством использования цифровых корпусных ресурсов, решающих многие вопросы в образовательной части. Для изучения языка, обогащения словарного запаса, в частности профессиональной направленности, разработаны цифровые платформы, программные средства которые обрабатывают текстовые данные и на их основе собирают необходимый материал, являющийся эффективным средством обучения.

Ключевые слова: корпусная лингвистика, корпуса, текст, лексика, грамматика, данные.

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This paper discusses the mechanisms of corpus linguistics and reviews the methods, experience of studying, analyzing, systematizing linguistic work through the use of digital corpus resources that solve many issues in the educational part. To learn the language, enrich the vocabulary, in particular, professional orientation, digital platforms have been developed, the software tools of which process text data and, on their basis, collect the necessary material, which is an effective teaching aid.

Keywords: Corpus linguistics, corpora, text, vocabulary, grammar, concordance, data.

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NEFT VA GAS SOHASI TILINI URGANISHDA YANGI YONDASHUV

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada korpus lingvistikasining mexanizmlari va usullari, ta'lim qismidagi ko'plab masalalarni hal qiladigan raqamli korpus resurslaridan foydalanish orqali lingvistik ishlarni o'rganish, tahlil qilish, tizimlashtirish tajribasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Tilni o'rganish, so'z boyligini boyitish, xususan, kasbiy yo'nalish, raqamli platformalar, matnli ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlovchi va ular asosida kerakli materialni to'playdigan dasturiy vositalar ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, bu samarali o'quv quroli xisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: korpus lingvistikasi, korpus, matn, lug'at, grammatika, ma'lumotlar.

At the moment, new methods of learning languages are being actively developed in accordance with scientific progress. A new turn in linguistics is the section of linguistics - corpus linguistics, the development of which is closely connected with the digital industry. There has been a sharp leap in the development of computer and information technologies. These possibilities began to be successfully used in linguistics. Thanks to the development and popularization of the global Internet, a huge number of users from different countries could use the data from the corpus [9]. A linguistic, or language, corpus of texts is understood as "a large, electronically presented, unified, structured, labeled, philologically competent array of linguistic data, designed to solve specific linguistic problems" [8]. The resources, tools, and techniques developed in the field of corpus linguistics play a particularly important role in many vocabulary studies. For example, balanced, representative corpora, such as the British National Corpus (BNC) and the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA), often serve as the starting point for vocabulary frequency counts and coverage measures. Corpus tools, such as word frequency profiling tools and concordancers, are the primary analytical tools used by vocabulary researchers [1]. When processing large volumes of texts in private terminology management, specialized software is used to protect against term attacks. The most interesting software tools of this kind are AntConc and Sketch Engine [5]. The Sketch Engine is a leading corpus tool. It is a set of software tools for corpus analysis developed by Lexical Computing Ltd [2-3].

Sketch Engine contains 500 ready-to-use corpora in 90+ languages, each having a size of up to 30 billion words to provide a truly representative sample of language [5]. Text analytics describes a set of linguistic, statistical, and machine learning techniques that model and structure the information content of textual sources for business intelligence, exploratory data analysis, research, or investigation. Text mining – a field located at the intersection of computer and information science, mathematics, and (computational) linguistics – promises not only to analyze large text corpora efficiently, but also to do so in a transparent and reproducible manner [7]. Text mining encompasses linguistic, statistical, and machine learning techniques, which can be used, in its final stage for analysis, visualization (via maps, charts, mind maps), for integration with structured data in databases or warehouses, for machine learning, etc [11].

The functions of the program (pic.1) allow to compose a concordance and subject it to all kinds of processing (Search), identify statistical collocates (Collocations), compile lists of words (Word List), analyze the lexical and syntactic compatibility of a word (Word Sketch), select illustrative sentences (Good Dictionary Example), compile a thesaurus (Thesaurus) and etc [8].

Text mining works in such a way that a separate material is formed from the text, containing key semantic, lexical and grammatical points. The information obtained can serve for the user as

explanatory, terminological, frequency, neological, thematic, phraseological dictionaries, depending on the specific function.

When loading any text, the user can study its structure thanks to a special tool. The words that are most repeated in the text are extracted from the text, and a list is formed from them. Thanks to this technology, students can study complex articles, manuals, messages, split them into separate words and study them as a dictionary (pic.2). This process facilitates the development of terminology.

This method of learning a language systematizes its various areas, provides the user with the opportunity to navigate the preferences of the information provided. It becomes easier to search for the necessary information. It becomes possible to filter out unnecessary or already familiar words.

Pic.1 - Functions of SketchEngine tool

The screenshot shows the 'WORDLIST' interface for the corpus 'Management & Economics in the Oil and Gas industry'. It displays a list of 30 most frequent nouns. The table below represents the data shown in the screenshot.

Noun	Frequency ? ↓	Noun	Frequency ? ↓
1 oil	7,455 ...	21 study	1,174 ...
2 gas	6,386 ...	22 system	1,166 ...
3 energy	3,246 ...	23 level	1,140 ...
4 production	3,004 ...	24 growth	1,088 ...
5 price	2,991 ...	25 result	1,074 ...
6 industry	2,075 ...	26 state	1,063 ...
7 management	2,044 ...	27 page	1,052 ...
8 company	1,877 ...	28 field	1,050 ...
9 development	1,743 ...	29 research	1,026 ...
10 model	1,686 ...	30 analysis	1,008 ...

Pic.2 - Gradation of the use of words in the selected corpus

When analyzing the oil and gas industry and downloading texts with oil and gas topics, a certain pattern was revealed. The share of educational text is almost half of all corpus texts (49%) and includes tutorials on the development of oil and gas fields. Scientific text (41%) - scientific articles and abstracts of dissertations that consider various aspects and methods of developing oil and gas fields. Technical text (10%) - the text of the instruction on safety rules in the exploration and

development of oil and gas fields [6]. All over the world, in higher education institutions, data from linguistic corpora are used in the preparation of various lecture courses and assignments for students. Many students themselves use corpus data when working on projects and homework. It can be assumed that students who are encouraged to independently study the language, its features and traits, master language competencies faster and more efficiently [9]. Sketch Engine helps to learn new words that can be found in certain professions, the functions of the corpus also help to recognize the meanings of words and the difference between synonyms, so that students use the most semantically appropriate words in speech and construction of texts. The use of the corpus helps to diversify the vocabulary, replenish it with professional terms.

The most groundbreaking advancements have been with the development of web-based corpus query systems, meaning that users can engage in corpus linguistics without needing to download the corpora or the software programs. For web corpora, this has been an essential development as it means users can easily and cheaply access ultra-large-scale corpora that would be too large and costly to distribute for download. This has untied corpus linguistics from private computers and moved it into a cloud-based, mobile environment. Indeed, it is now possible to make a rapid query of a ten-billion-word corpus of any of the world's major languages simply through using an Internet connected device [4].

Text mining and the use of corpora help in systematizing linguistic knowledge, automating the text processing process and searching for corpora of a certain orientation. The largest percentage of existing corpora belongs to the educational segment, thus, the linguistic corpus is a means for solving not only scientific, but also educational and methodological problems. Sketch Engine has already helped many students in the educational process, replaced them with a dictionary of professional terms, allowed them to learn their future profession not only in their native language, but also in a foreign language, which will allow future specialists to be multilingual. The benefits of its application in various fields are beyond doubt, although the theoretical basis has not yet been fully developed. That is why scientists still cannot answer the question: "What is corpus linguistics: a new scientific discipline or just an information resource?" We hope that soon the answer to this question will be found and corpus linguistics will become an independent scientific discipline.

At the moment, a special dictionary is under development, the content of which covers the terminology characteristic of the directions "Management" and "Economics" and the purpose of which is to study by students and specialists previously unknown terms and enrich the professional vocabulary. Getting data for the dictionary is based on the use of the Sketch Engine electronic tool. The dictionary compilation technology has the following steps:

1. Search for articles on the subject of "Economics" and "Management";
2. Uploading articles to the SketchEngine corpus;
3. Getting a list of the most frequently occurring words/phrases in uploaded articles;
4. Analysis of the received list;
5. Search for the meaning of the given words and phrases, an example of use;
6. Translation of the information received into Russian and Uzbek with the maximum preservation of meaning;
7. Drawing up a tabular version of the dictionary, alphabetical sorting, numbering.

Tab.1 Fragment of the compiled dictionary

Exploratory well	A deep test hole drilled by oil and gas exploration companies to locate proven reserves of recoverable gas and oil, both onshore and offshore.
Рус: Разведочная скважина	Example: Drilling an exploratory well is an expensive, time consuming effort. Глубокая пробная скважина, пробуренная компаниями по разведке нефти и газа для определения доказанных запасов извлекаемого газа и нефти как на суше, так и на шельфе.
Uzb: Izlanish quduqi	Пример: Бурение разведочной скважины - дорогостоящее и отнимающее много времени мероприятие.

	<p>Quruqlikda ham, dengizda ham qazib olinadigan gaz va neftning tasdiqlangan zahiralarini aniqlash uchun neft va gaz qidiruvi kompaniyalari tomonidan burg'ulangan chuqur sinov teshigi.</p> <p>Masalan: Qidiruv qudug'ini burg'ulash qimmat, ko'p vaqt talab qiladigan harakatdir.</p>
<p>Pipeline system</p> <p>Рус: Трубопроводная система</p> <p>Uzb: Quvur liniyasi tizimi</p>	<p>An interconnected system of underwater pipelines, their dimensions, supports, shut-off valves, all non-removable connecting parts, associated protective systems and a corrosion protection system.</p> <p>Example: The pipeline system, inherited from USSR, has Russian Federation as its central core.</p> <p>Взаимосвязанная система подводных трубопроводов, их размеры, опоры, запорная арматура, все несъемные соединительные детали, связанные с ней защитные системы и система защиты от коррозии.</p> <p>Пример: Трубопроводная система, унаследованная от СССР, имеет в качестве центрального ядра Российскую Федерацию.</p> <p>Suv osti quvurlarining o'zaro bog'liq tizimi, ularning o'lchamlari, tayanchlari, o'chirish klapanlari, barcha olinmaydigan ulanish qismlari, u bilan bog'liq himoya tizimlari va korroziyadan himoya qilish tizimi.ushbu sohada birinchi toifadir).</p> <p>Masalan: SSSR dan meros bo'lib o'tgan quvur tizimi Markaziy yadro sifatida Rossiya Federatsiyasiga ega.</p>

Active work is underway to compile and refine the elements of the dictionary; by now, 50% of the total work on compiling the dictionary has been completed. The processing of words and phrases, the search for their semantic meaning and an example of the use of the given language units are carried out. Each word/phrase from the dictionary is subject to translation from English into Russian and Uzbek. About 400 words/phrases have already been processed and included in the dictionary.

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